

Comprehensive optical monitoring of photopolymer curing for additive manufacturing of diffractive elements

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Abstract: Diffractive optical elements (DOE) offer a wide range of possibilities, from beam shaping to augmented reality and neural networks. Additive manufacturing using photopolymerization curing shows great potential for manufacturing customizable DOEs at low cost. To design and fabricate these, it is essential to monitor both the dynamic evolution of the curing process as well as its spatial distribution during and after curing. To this end, we propose an all-optical monitoring platform comprising a “focused line refractive index microscopy” (FLRIM) technique based on total internal reflection at a prism interface and a large field-of-view interferometric imager, more specifically a “lateral-shearing interferometric microscopy” (LIM) technique. The FLRIM enables dynamic in-situ spatio-temporal quantitative measurements of refractive index (RI) during the curing process, while the LIM technique provides quantitative information of 2D structures by measuring the transmitted phase with high sensitivity via multi-angle illumination. An ultraviolet “digital micromirror device” (DMD) projector is used to photopolymerize pixelated 2D structures. By using the proposed monitoring platform, we investigate the resulting photopolymer structures in-situ during several local curing steps, and, additionally, before and after a global post-curing. Besides showing the capabilities of our technology, we additionally demonstrate that there is potential to fabricate DOEs on a single photopolymer by exploiting tunable local RI changes.

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1. Introduction

Diffractive optical elements (DOEs) [1] are micro- or nano-structured elements designed to map spatial and/or angular light distributions into desired patterns. They are used in many scientific and industrial applications, for example as input couplers to optical waveguides [2]; for wavefront [3] or beam shaping [4]; for diffractive optical neural networks [5]; and have even been expanded to terahertz optics [6,7].

DOEs are typically manufactured [1] using precision mechanical machining [8], classic lithographic techniques, or a combination thereof [9], and are then often complemented with replication techniques [8,9] to transfer the structure of a high-quality master to a large volume of DOEs. These techniques have several limitations, such as unsuitability for 3D structures, quantization of height levels that can be used to achieve the desired diffraction effects, maximum possible size of the DOEs and being time consuming and expensive. Therefore, there is ongoing research to develop new fabrication techniques that overcome some of these limitations, allowing for improved DOEs and making application-specific designs easier.

For example, on the nm^2 to μm^2 scale, scanning probe lithography [2] is one possible fabrication technique for achieving continuous height levels. It has been demonstrated for fabrication of analogue surface shapes, consisting of an arbitrary superposition of sinewaves in two dimensions, so called “Fourier surfaces”. Unfortunately, the high precision of this technique is limited to small fabrication area ($\approx \mu\text{m}^2$). For 3D structures, two photon polymerization lithography was demonstrated for fabrication of a variety of meta surfaces [10,11], e.g., for beam shaping [12], achromatic metalenses [13] or birefringent optical-retarders [14], while also being limited in area ($\approx \mu\text{m}^2$) and volume ($\approx \mu\text{m}^3$).

On the mm^2 and cm^2 scale, interferometric lithography [15–18] can be used for fabrication of scalable periodic gratings. On the other hand, additive manufacturing techniques could become a key to enable fast, large-scale, and cost-efficient fabrication of custom DOEs, allowing for shapes with a large number of height levels. More specifically, photopolymerization is a well-established technique in additive manufacturing and could be a cost-efficient approach for manufacturing of custom optics [19] and variable DOEs. It has already become a proven technology for fabrication of classical optical components [20,21], ranging, e.g., from μm^3 sized phase elements for laser beam shaping [22] to full mm^3 sized optical lenses [23,24].

Recently, photopolymerization has specifically been used in DOE manufacturing processes. Simple diffractive gratings can directly be fabricated using commercially available 3D resin printers [25]. More complex DOEs were demonstrated by using additive manufacturing to create free-form molds for casting, and then immersing the cast and cured hundreds of micrometers thick photopolymer structure in a near refractive index (RI) matched liquid [3], or inside another cured nearly RI matched polymer [26]. Light traveling through these structures experiences a change in its phase, which is commonly expressed in terms of optical path length (OPL), which is the product of geometrical path length and RI along this path. The DOE effect then depends on the locally varying optical path difference (OPD) that is introduced by the whole structure onto the wavefront of the beam. In simple terms, it depends on changes of the product of geometry and RI. As a result, the surface shapes with μm -scale thickness variations can create nanometric and wavelength scale OPDs (tens to hundreds of nanometers) for RI differences in the range of 10^{-3} to 10^{-5} .

One of the challenges for these examples is that they are fabricated in a multi-step process requiring a combination of different techniques and materials [3,26], increasing the number of processes which need to be controlled. In the case of using photopolymerization, the RI of the cured photopolymer structures strongly depends on the curing process parameters. When curing a photopolymer, carbon double bonds of the monomer, i.e. single molecules, are broken up to create single bonds and create polymer chains, i.e. thousands of molecules connected, reducing the RI due to molar refraction [27]. At the same time, a closer packing of entangled polymer chains compared to the mobile liquid monomer state increases the density of the polymer, overall causing a rise of the RI of cured areas [28–31].

Herein the curing grade is directly related to the UV irradiance used for curing, which in turn affects the resulting RI. Therefore, a local or time dependent variation of the irradiance during curing can result in variations of the RI. Recently, tunable RI changes have been demonstrated using multi-photon polymerization, where high power focused laser beams enabled tuning of RI of fabricated micro-lenses [32]. The higher the dosage of the laser beam, the higher the RI, surpassing even the ones achieved with standard UV polymerization. Another study has shown that the grade of polymerization and therefore the RI can also be increased through subsequent UV post-curing or thermal baking processes, with both having similar effects until a saturation is reached [33]. Furthermore, thermal post-curing has been shown to also influence mechanical properties of photopolymerized objects [34].

It is thus crucial to investigate the development of RI during initial and subsequent exposure steps, and the differences in RI between unexposed, partially exposed and unexposed areas. This

process may vary when applying additional curing to 2D structures consisting of a combination of cured and uncured structures. For this purpose, new monitoring techniques are necessary which help us investigate if RIs vary between areas when exposed first, at a second stage, or after a final uniform post-curing. If this hypothesis is confirmed, these effects could be used to create DOEs using only a single type of photopolymer, by making use of local differences after subsequent curing and post-curing steps, which could pave the way towards fabrication of a new generation of DOE.

To gain knowledge about the nature of the photopolymerization processes, we propose an all-optical monitoring platform for studying the tunable degree of polymerization and the development of RI on a large - mm² - scale. This platform comprises a “focused line RI microscopy” (FLRIM) technique based on total internal reflection at a prism interface [35], and a large field-of-view interferometric imager, that is a “lateral-shearing interferometric microscopy” (LIM) technique. By combining these techniques, we will monitor both the dynamic evolution of the photopolymerization process, as well as its spatial distribution, both during and after curing.

The FLRIM is based on the principle of Abbe refractometry, relating the critical angle of total internal reflection at a prism-sample-interface to the sample RI. The underlying principle has recently been further developed in “Scanning focused refractive-index microscopy” (SFRIM) [36], using a beam focused to single spot on a prism-photopolymer-interface. Using a pixel line detector, the critical angle inside the focused beam can be detected and the RI at the focus spot calculated. SFRIM offers high RI resolution but comes with several drawbacks, especially for spatio-temporal measurements. The point shaped focus requires scanning of the sample to extract the spatial RI information in one or two dimensions. Furthermore, the scanning limits the time resolution of RI profiles, while additionally making the in-situ curing measurements more complex, as the sample is moving in the original setup. The FLRIM expands upon the concept of SFRIM by using a focused line along which the RI can be measured at the photopolymer-prism-interface, enabling for spatio-temporal measurements of RI changes during curing with the UV DMD projector.

Since the FLRIM measurements are limited to the prism-photopolymer-interface, we complement it with the LIM technique to image the phase of light transmitted through the structure, as this governs the diffractive properties of the structures in the far field. Quantitative phase imaging (QPI) [37–43] is an ideal technique to image these structures and their OPDs at the nanometric scale with high contrast and sensitivity. QPI has been demonstrated for imaging structures inside the sample volume [44–47], such as defects, impurities, or RI changes. Furthermore, it has been specifically demonstrated for the characterization of laser induced RI changes [47–52], which are of the same order of magnitude as those obtained by curing. In previous work, we have demonstrated the LIM technique for characterization of transparent dielectric materials [53–55] and semi-transparent ultra-thin metal-films [56]. For this work specifically, we will further improve the sensitivity by averaging several phase images generated using sequential multi-angle illumination from a fiber-optic-bundle [55], which is essential to visualize the nanometric changes in OPL.

We then use the FLRIM to perform spatio-temporal measurements of the RI of a photopolymer (Autodesk Ember PR48). After an initial curing step, RI differences in the 10⁻² to 10⁻³ range between fully cured and uncured areas are measured, which is a typical upper limit for RI differences between cured and uncured photopolymer. On top of that, we analyze the RI values after subsequent UV post-curing steps, showing that a residual RI difference in the 10⁻³ to 10⁻⁵ range remains between the initially exposed areas and the background.

In a follow-up experiment, we encapsulate a layer of photopolymer between two high quality glass slides using a spacer of known thickness, and imprint different 2D patterns using the projector. We fabricate a set of samples with and without a post curing step, using uniform diffuse illumination with an LED or the same pixelated UV DMD projector, and then image the resulting

phase with the LIM technique. Herein, we can again observe that UV post-curing cannot fully homogenize the initially imprinted structures, in agreement with the FLRIM measurements.

Therefore, our proposed monitoring platform ultimately proves our initial hypothesis and demonstrates that DOEs can be created using only a single type of photopolymer, by making use of local differences in curing grade and global post curing, paving the way towards to a new generation of DOE.

2. Dynamic diffraction during photopolymer curing

In an initial experiment, we demonstrate that curing of a photopolymer (Autodesk Ember PR48) with the UV DMD (Wintech Pro4500; 405 nm; $40 \times 40 \mu\text{m}^2$ projected pixel size) creates a diffraction grating as defined by the illumination pattern. Figure 1(a) shows a color-image of the far-field diffraction pattern on a grating inscribed in photopolymer with the UV projector, illuminated with a white light laser. The grating consists of vertical stripes, with the illumination pattern for curing shown in the overlay in Fig. 1(b). The vertical stripes therefore create a horizontal diffraction pattern, where the distance between diffraction orders is defined by the grating-period of the stripes. However, it can be observed that the diffraction pattern in Fig. 1(a) also contains an additional vertical diffraction component. When observing the illumination pattern shown in Fig. 1(b), a small variation of intensity within the stripes can be observed, which is given by the pixel-structure of the projector. This small variation is already sufficient to create changes in RI that add an additional diffraction effect along the vertical axis, resulting in a 2D diffraction pattern. The distances of the diffraction orders shown in Fig. 1(a) match the pixelated illumination distribution with a horizontal grating period of two pixels for the stripes (diffraction orders closer together) and a grating period of one pixel within the stripes (diffraction orders further apart).

Fig. 1. Analysis of diffraction patterns on photopolymer samples by cured structured illumination. a) Spatial diffraction pattern created by a white light laser on cured stripes, demonstrating 2D diffraction with two orthogonal grating constants, as given by the pixelated curing structure shown in inset (b). c) Setup for structured curing of encapsulated photopolymer and parallel diffraction analysis. d) temporal diffraction pattern captured on different times during curing with e) quantized analysis of intensity over diffraction orders.

This work further presents results from an advanced setup sketched in Fig. 1(c) enabling a time resolved analysis of the diffraction during curing. An encapsulated photopolymer sample

is illuminated from below through a transparent substrate with structured illumination using the UV DMD projector. At the same time, a laser beam is superimposed to the structured UV illumination, transmitting through the imprinted photopolymer structures for diffraction analysis. The far field diffraction pattern is captured on a camera image sensor to evaluate the evolution of the diffraction pattern and diffraction order intensities over time. Whereas the image in Fig. 1(a) only shows the resulting diffraction pattern after curing, Fig. 1(d) shows snapshots of the diffraction pattern with 10 frames per second, revealing a change of the diffraction pattern over the time of the curing process. Starting with the initial un-diffracted zero-order laser spot before curing, the time-varying creation and suppression of diffraction orders is visible, showing a dynamic transition of the diffractive grating structure.

The diagram in Fig. 1(e) shows graphs of the evolution of the diffraction order intensities as shown in Fig. 1(d). At the beginning, before any structure is inscribed, only the un-diffracted zero-order is present. With the curing starting at $t = 0.8$ s, the intensity of the zeroth order decreases as the intensity of the first order increases. After some more time, the first order vanishes again while the zero-order increases in intensity again. The periodic intensity variation of diffraction orders indicates a varying phase grating, which is caused by changes of the RI during the curing process. Together with the RI, the encapsulation of the sample defines the geometrical path along which the phase of light is modified.

This is sketched in Fig. 2, showing a photopolymer sample with uncured resin with $n_{monomer}$, with additional embedded structures of cured photopolymer with a higher RI $n_{polymer}$. As the light beam passes through the cured and uncured areas inside the sample, the varying RI results in an OPD (blue box, Fig. 2(b)), thus leading to distortions of the wavefront after the sample. For the thin sample investigated in this work, where diffraction effects within the sample itself can be neglected, this can be interpreted in terms of rays passing straight through, accumulating OPD as an integral of the RI along the geometrical path.

Fig. 2. Sketch indicating complementary approaches of the analysis of phase gratings by structured curing of photopolymers: A cured structure with $n_{polymer}$ is embedded in an uncured or partially cured liquid photopolymer resin with $n_{monomer}$, with $n_{polymer}$ decreasing with distance to the initial illuminated surface; FLRIM offers measurement of absolute RI at the (a) sample-substrate-interface; LIM Phase imaging microscope detects (b) the output phase and wavefront distortion in terms of the OPD.

To understand these diffraction effects and to analyze this underlying phase grating, we propose an all-optical monitoring platform comprising a “focused line refractive index microscopy” (FLRIM) technique based on total internal reflection at a prism interface, and a large field-of-view interferometric imager, more specifically a “lateral-shearing interferometric microscopy” (LIM) technique. Using the FLRIM technique, we perform dynamic spatio-temporal measurements of the RI of a photopolymer (Autodesk Ember PR48), therefore quantitatively showing that the RI variations are the source of the phase grating. However, the FLRIM measurements are limited to the prism-polymer-interface (red box, Fig. 2(a)) and the evanescent field of the beam, while

the phase grating leading to the observed far field diffraction pattern is a volumetric effect (blue box, Fig. 2(b)), that goes beyond the RI information that is measured with the FLRIM setup at the prism interface. Therefore, the complementary LIM imaging technique is used to visualize the structures which cause the far field diffraction pattern. Both techniques and the related measurements will be described in the following sections.

3. Quantitative in-situ measurement of refractive index

3.1. Focused Line Refractive index microscopy (FLRIM)

Figure 3(a) shows a scheme of the “Focused Line Refractive index microscopy” (FLRIM) [35] with all extensions, including structured curing, RI measurements, and optional analysis of diffractive patterns (such as the ones described in Fig. 1).

Fig. 3. a) Scheme of FLRIM for temporal and spatial analysis of refractive index and diffraction during UV curing. b) Workflow for extracting the RI profile from raw image data: b-I) Real intensity image of the camera, which needs to be processed column-wise. The columns show the intensity profiles following Fresnel equations. b-II) Extracted intensity profile (orange), to which ideal an ideal Fresnel profile (examples in blue) is fitted, determining the critical angle, and thus the RI for that column and point along the focus line. b-III) Final refractive index profile along focus line.

The core principle of FLRIM remains the measurement of the critical angle of total internal reflection of the prism (1) and sample (3) to calculate the RI. The input beam (2) is focused by a cylinder lens through a high index prism onto the prism-sample-interface. This creates a ray fan along a line shaped focus, enabling a RI measurement along a 1D profile. According to Snell’s law, depending on the incident angle and RI on both sides of the interface, some rays of the ray fan are transmitted through the sample, while the rest experiences total internal reflection (TIR).

As the rays coupled out into the sample are missing in the reflected beam, it contains the angular intensity profile of the Fresnel reflection. A camera captures the reflected beam's (4) intensity distribution, and by detecting the boundary between the transmitted and TIR rays on the sensor, the critical angle of total internal reflection can be extracted. After calibration using the known RI of the prism (Material N-SF11; $n = 1.78$ at D-Line), an absolute RI can be assigned to each point along the focused line, creating a 1D RI profile. By using a focus line and a camera instead of a pixel line detector, improvements compared to SFRIM [36], the RI profile along the line shaped focus can be measured in one shot. Continuous imaging with multiple frames per second enables the live analysis of the curing process with temporal and spatial resolution. With this combination of spatio-temporal curing, spatio-temporal RI measurement and spatio-temporal diffraction recording, a detailed analysis of the curing process is possible.

By clipping the prism of FLRIM on the bottom and creating an input window, the setup can be combined with the structured UV illumination curing, and optionally with a diffraction analysis, as shown in Fig. 3(a). The structured illumination from the UV DMD projector then cures the liquid photopolymer samples on the prism interface. With the imaging optics, the pixel size on sample can be tuned from $50\ \mu\text{m}$ to $30\ \mu\text{m}$, but is fixed to $40\ \mu\text{m}$ for the samples investigated in this work. The projector uses a UV LED at 405 nm and achieves irradiances of up to $20\ \text{mW}/\text{cm}^2$ (average over a mask with all pixels active). Inset (5) in Fig. 3(a) shows bright violet stripes as curing mask to write a diffraction grating into the encapsulated photopolymer, with the green laser for diffraction analysis being visible as well. The photopolymer sample is covered with a glass slide to remove the meniscus of the liquid photopolymer and to create a flat top surface, eliminating optical distortions from the far-field diffraction pattern (6), which can be captured by another separate camera, enabling an analysis as shown in Fig. 1. Inset (7) in Fig. 3(a) sketches a top view onto the prism with a sample with three stripes of high RI surrounded by areas of low RI. The red line indicates the beam focus. For the three stripes with high RI, the critical angle of total internal reflection is larger, so more light is coupled out from the prism into the sample, which is implied by variation of the red color on the right.

The procedure to recover the RI along the focus line, i.e., processing each column of the camera, is visualized in Fig. 3(b): Fig. 3(b-I) shows a real intensity image of the camera of the FLRIM setup. The dark section across the bottom of the image related to the low base RI of the photopolymer. There are six distinct columns protruding from the dark section to the top of the image, which shows the higher RI of cured stripes in the photopolymer sample. The angular intensity profile along the orange line is shown in Fig. 3(b-II). For comparison, the dashed blue lines show "ideal" simulated intensity profiles for a range of photopolymer RI values as calculated with Fresnel equations. As can be seen, the real experimental profile is affected by lots of noise and the critical angle cannot be determined easily. A least square fit between the experimental data and ideal Fresnel profiles gives an optimum, which translates into the final RI for this column of the focus line. This fitting is repeated for each column, assigning a RI to each point along the focus line. The graph in Fig. 3(b-III) shows the resulting extracted RI profile along the focus line.

While images are captured with high framerates and temporal information is measured with high time-resolution, the least square fit takes around 4s for all 1024 columns to be processed. These computing times do not limit our study. However, for future applications requiring real-time processing and analysis, this can be achieved using parallelized GPU processing, or using a neural network, as it was shown in Ref. [35].

3.2. FLRIM analysis of 1D grating structure

Figure 4(a) offers a visualization of the spatial (horizontal axis) and temporal (vertical axis) development of the RI, i.e., curing state of the photopolymer (Autodesk Ember PR48) during multiple UV illuminations. The white empty spaces in the plot indicate breaks between the different curing segments and are implemented to manually be able to sync data acquisition

and structured illumination. Structured illumination with alternating bright and dark pixels creates thin cured structures, with the photopolymer in between the illuminated pixels remaining partially uncured. With additional repeated structured UV illuminations using the same mask, the illuminated areas reach a higher RI, while the photopolymer in the dark regions in between also experiences some curing due to crosstalk, e.g., scattering within the photopolymer or additional isometric curing spread.

Fig. 4. FLRIM analysis of 1D grating structure: a) Spatio-temporal evolution of the RI, allowing for both b) temporal and c) spatial RI profiles during the UV curing by structured illumination.

The diagram in Fig. 4(b) shows the temporal RI evolution of an illuminated pixel (position $-250 \mu\text{m}$; blue) in comparison to a neighboring dark pixel (position $-290 \mu\text{m}$, orange). The base RI prior to the first illumination is the same for both lines at $n = 1.47$. With the first illumination, the RI increases significantly for illuminated areas, but at the same time an increase in RI can also be observed for dark areas. For each structured illumination, the RI increases in both illuminated and dark areas, with the cured lines effectively become wider and blooming into the dark areas, slowly reducing the difference of $\Delta n = 0.01$ after the first illumination to approximately $\Delta n = 0.005$ after the second structured illumination.

The relative RI distribution of the profile at $t = 40$ s (black arrow) is visualized in Fig. 4(c) showing the periodic structure with a smooth RI transition between the illuminated and the dark areas. With each illumination step, the RI difference becomes smaller.

At $t = 65$ s post curing is introduced, with all pixels of the UV projector being turned on for uniform UV-exposure of this grating structure. With post curing, the previously dark, but already partially cured, areas are now intentionally cured, and this irradiation also leads to curing of areas adjacent to the pattern. Although the RI difference between previously illuminated and previously dark areas decreases significantly now, full homogenization is not achieved. The residual RI difference after post curing goes down to 10^{-3} , reaching the sensitivity limit of the FLRIM setup.

4. Quantitative phase imaging (QPI) of curing structures

4.1. Lateral-shearing interferometric microscopy (LIM) with multi-angle illumination

Figure 5. Shows the phase imaging microscope consisting of objective (OBJ, $f' = 18$ mm) and tube lens (TL, $f' = 200$ mm), crossed linear polarizers (P1, P2), Savart plates (SP1, SP2) and an image sensor array (ISA). The polarizers and Savart Plates are used to implement a lateral-shearing interferometric microscopy (LIM) scheme for quantitative phase imaging, which has been demonstrated in our previous works [53–56].

Fig. 5. Lateral-shearing interferometric microscope (LIM) with multi-angle illumination: Objective (OBJ) and tube lens (TL), linear polarizers (P1, P2), Savart plates (SP1, SP2) and image sensor array (ISA). Tilt in SP1 is used to introduce a controllable phase shift between polarizations, enabling phase-shifting interferometry to calculate OPD images [53–56]. A fiber-optic-bundle (FOB) with fiber collimator (COL) is used for illumination from multiple directions (e.g. shown in red, green). Illumination rays transmitted through sample features are displayed with reduced translucency. Angled illumination creates lateral shifts $\delta(\Delta z)$ for planes that are out-of-focus by Δz . Averaging respective fiber images A . . . F will improve quality for in-focus features, whereas shifted out-of-focus features are blurred and suppressed.

The samples analyzed here consist of multiple interfaces, i.e., two glass slides embedding the structure of interest. Using a collimated illumination beam with relatively low 10x magnification, the background phase signal contributions from the interfaces and volumes add up towards the phase noise in the final OPD image, even when they are out-of-focus.

To alleviate this problem, we implemented the multi-angle illumination and averaging technique which we demonstrated before in a lens-free imaging configuration to reduce the OPD signals

from out-of-focus planes [55]. A fiber-optic-bundle (FOB) with fiber collimator (COL) is used for illuminating the sample from multiple directions (e.g. shown in red, green). The central fiber and the six outermost fibers (A to F) of the FOB are used in a hexagonal distribution to independently illuminate the sample on-axis or with an angle α to the z axis, and to reconstruct the respective OPD images using phase-shifting interferometry. When using this angled illuminations, out-of-focus features experience lateral shifts $\delta(\Delta z)$ relative to the on-axis illumination beams, with $\delta(\Delta z)$ linearly increasing with defocus Δz . For the sequentially recorded OPD images with the different fibers of the FOB, an offset pattern according to the pattern of the FOB can be observed for out-of-focus features, as shown in Fig. 5, whereas in-focus features are overlapping. By averaging the individual OPD images, a high-quality image with reduced noise and improved axial resolution is obtained, as in-focus features are preserved, and other planes are suppressed.

4.2. Phase imaging of structures with varying curing grade

To analyze the RI difference between cured and uncured areas, before and after post-curing, we encapsulate a layer of photopolymer (Autodesk Ember PR48) between two high quality glass slides using a spacer of 80 μm thickness and imprint a range of cured structure using the UV DMD projector, as shown in Fig. 6.

Fig. 6. (a) Liquid resin (Monomer, yellow) embedded between two high quality glass slides, separated by an 80 μm spacer. Structured DMD illumination (blue, 5 s) to cure the polymer (orange). (b) Scheme of optical path differences by varying curing grade: Measurement beam (red arrows) with input phase ϕ_{in} passing through higher RI (n_{Poly}) and lower RI (n_{Mono}), resulting in output phase ϕ_{out} . (c) Application of additional global post-curing with UV LED exposure (4 min), where the initially cured structures are expected to remain with a slightly higher RI. (d) Global post-curing with all pixels of DMD turned on (30 s), globally imprinting a pixel structure, where the initially cured structures are expected to remain with slightly higher RI.

We fabricate test-structures without global post curing (Fig. 6. (a)), which are exposed for 5 seconds to structured illumination from the DMD UV projector ($\lambda = 405 \text{ nm}$, 20 mW/cm^2). Each of the test-structures is surrounded with a square frame of cured pixels to prevent leaking of the liquid photopolymer. Using the proposed technique, OPD images of the samples are generated to make the inscribed phase structures (Fig. 6. (b)) visible. We additionally fabricate copies of the same structures for investigating the RI and OPDs after sub-sequent post-curing steps, using 4

min of global diffuse LED illumination (Fig. 6. (c)) or 30 s illumination with the same projector (Fig. 6. (d)).

Figure 7 shows the results on a checkerboard pattern, where every second pixel is turned on. The initial cured structure is shown in a), with horizontal OPD profile in b) and zoom in c). The same is displayed for another sample with an equivalent structure with additional LED post-curing in d), e) and f). Colormap contrasts are optimized for each related image. Looking at the contours of the structure in Fig. 7(a), a partial curing can be observed at the areas between two exposed pixels. The same type of contouring can be observed after post-curing in Fig. 7(d). Overall, the pixel structure is clearly visible in both samples, including the central indentation of the DMD pixel, even in the post-cured structure. It can be concluded that post-curing does not homogenize the RI of the background and the initially imprinted structures, and therefore will not erase the structures. Comparing the OPD profile before and after post-curing, the magnitude of the signals is reduced approximately by a factor of 10 during the post curing step, in agreement with RI changes measured by the FLRIM setup.

Fig. 7. OPD images of checkerboard structure. a) OPD image of cured checkerboard structure in liquid photopolymer, b) extracted horizontal OPD profile along the center of the structure and c) zoom in on cured pixels. d) OPD image after homogeneous post curing, checkerboard still visible, e) OPD profile along the post cured structure and f) zoom in on post-cured checkerboard.

For further analysis, we fabricated another type of sample with structures made up of larger 5-by-5-pixel squares, as shown in Fig. 8, comparing cured structures in liquid photopolymer (Fig. 8(a)) with homogenous LED post-curing using LED illumination (Fig. 8(b)) or with the

pixelated DMD projector (Fig. 8(c)). Comparing the different curing states of the 5-by-5 square pattern in Fig. 8(a)-(c), the pixels and their central indentations are visible before and after post-curing, with the only difference being that the DMD post-curing introduces the pixel pattern also into the background. Signals after post-curing are one order of magnitude smaller, same as observed for the previous structure. Comparing the shape of the structure before (Fig. 8(a)) and after (Fig. 8(b)-(c)) post-curing, no notable lateral deformation can be observed. However, when looking at the corners where two 5×5 squares are connected, both post-cured samples show positive or negative OPD signals, with the sign depending on the direction of the connection relative to the shear, which in this setup is horizontal. For a horizontal shearing direction, the axes for x and y polarizations are oriented at $\pm 45^\circ$, as indicated in Fig. 8. Therefore, it can be concluded that the sign of the signal depends on which of the two polarizations is aligned with the structure. Diagonal connections from the top left to the bottom right (x-pol., $+45^\circ$) give positive signal, whereas the other diagonal direction (y-pol., -45°) gives a negative signal of same magnitude. Corners without connected pixels also demonstrate this behavior, however, with weaker signals. Before post-curing, these types of signals were not visible. Since the measured signals are the OPD between the orthogonal polarizations, these observations indicate the presence of structural birefringence in the sample.

Fig. 8. 5-by-5 pixels checkerboard pattern in different curing states: a) cured structure in liquid photopolymer, b) with global LED post-curing and c) with DMD illuminated post-curing.

To further investigate this birefringence effect, we fabricate structures with anisotropic geometry consisting of concentric arc segments, with results being shown in Fig. 9. For the initially cured structures (Fig. 9(a)), the arc segments give the same type of positive and negative OPD signals

independent of orientation, as expected from the differential measurement scheme. Within the structures, only the edges of the pixels and central indentations create any OPD signal. This changes once post-curing is introduced in Fig. 9(b)-(c), with a strong directional effect being observed. The large arcs show a strong uniform birefringent background signal, with the sign changing with their orientation with regards to the polarization, with the signal being slightly smaller for the shorter arc segments. When interpreting the images, it must be emphasized here again that the images are of differential nature, i.e., the observed positive and negative background signal and directional dependence would not appear in a sample with isotropic RI. The magnitude of the birefringent OPD signal of the arc segments is around ± 20 nm, which is approximately a $\lambda/30$ order of magnitude, which is larger than the residual OPD signals observed for the post-cured structures.

Fig. 9. Arc segments a) without post-curing, with b) global LED post-curing and c) DMD projector post-curing.

5. Discussion

Both the FLRIM as well as the phase imaging measurements demonstrate that varying structured illumination and therefore curing grade of a single photopolymer can be used to create changes in RI, which results in phase changes of transmitted light.

We have further demonstrated that even after post curing, any initially exposed structure remains visible and full homogenization of the photopolymer is not achieved. This effect could potentially be used to manufacture fully cured and stable DOE in photopolymers, where the small remaining RI difference can be used along μm thick structures to create phase gratings with wavelength sized optical path differences. Herein the thickness and grade of post-curing could be used to tune the magnitude of the phase and therefore the diffraction efficiency of the different orders, as shown in Fig. 1.

These residual RI differences may be related to reduced mobility of the already existing polymer chains in the initially cured structures, affecting shrinkage during sequential curing steps of the rest of the photopolymer. Consequently, this leads to a slightly lower RI in post-cured areas.

Additionally, the phase imaging demonstrates structural birefringence depending on the shape and orientation of the polymer structures. To explain this effect, one may consider that the structures investigated in this work are embedded between two glass slides. During sequential

post-curing, shrinking of the polymer is only possible in the lateral directions, as the vertical dimension is fixed through the glass slides and the already imprinted structures. During the additional post-curing, the previously cured structures, as well as the respective surrounding frames, affect the in-plane shrinkage of the whole photopolymer volume. This may in turn cause anisotropic mechanical stress depending on the structures' size and orientation and lead to the observed structural stress birefringence. A previous investigation by Bombenger et. al. [57] supports this hypothesis.

For a comprehensive analysis, the observed effects, i.e. the residual RI difference, the birefringence, the possible relation between them and their origins, need to be further investigated and validated in future work.

6. Summary and outlook

In summary, in order to gain knowledge about the nature of the photopolymerization processes, and to investigate the tunable degree of polymerization, and the development of RI on a large - mm² - scale, we demonstrated an all-optical monitoring platform in this paper: The “focused line refractive index microscopy” (FLRIM) technique enables spatio-temporal quantitative measurements of RI at the prism interface during the curing process, while the “lateral-shearing interferometric microscopy” (LIM) technique visualized the phase of light transmitted through the whole volume.

Using this analysis platform, we have demonstrated that a residual RI difference persists even after post-curing, using different structures and types of post-curing. Therefore, it is possible to create DOEs using a combination of an initial exposure and post-curing, i.e. “immersing” cured structures in a post-curing volume, as demonstrated before using an immersion liquid [3] or immersion polymer [26]. Using micrometer sized structures, the residual RI differences, in the 10⁻³ to 10⁻⁵ range, could be used to create wavelength sized optical path differences, enabling new ways to manufacture phase-DOEs.

In summary, the proposed combination of techniques allows in-situ measurement of the absolute spatio-temporal RI during structured curing. This, combined with the analysis of the full phase response, enables not only precise characterization, but in the future, it will allow tuning of custom diffractive optical elements.

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- R.T. and V.P. are coinventors of granted patent US 11686680 B2, while S.H., R.T. and V.P. of patent application EP23382669.2, both related to phase imaging technology presented in this paper.
- M.R. and A.H. declare no conflicts of interest.

Author Contributions (CREDIT)

- S.H.: Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Formal analysis, Investigation, Resources, Visualization, Data Curation, Writing - Original Draft, Writing - Review & Editing;
- M.R.: Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Formal analysis, Investigation, Resources, Visualization, Data Curation, Writing - Original Draft, Writing - Review & Editing;
- R.T.: Conceptualization, Software, Writing - Review & Editing, Supervision;
- A.H.: Conceptualization, Writing - Review & Editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition;
- V.P.: Conceptualization, Writing - Review & Editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition;

Data availability.

- The data related to the presented “FLRIM” technique can be provided upon reasonable request to M.R. or A.H.
- The data related to “LIM” technique are stored on ICFO servers and can be provided upon reasonable request to S.H., R.T. or V.P.

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